

STRENGTHENING ECOLOGY OF CITIZENSHIP AS A SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This article discusses the reality of the current destruction of nature caused by various aspects of human action. The virtue of civic virtue in the environmental field is getting lower and the decline of morals is characterized by the widespread destruction of nature through various actions, the indiscriminate disposal of garbage and industrial waste, the decline in the quality of fresh air and clear water. This is a condition that reinforces the attention of all parties will be important and urgent efforts to strengthen conservation awareness and maintain the balance of the environment so that the balance can still be maintained and maintained. This condition certainly requires an alternative step solution that includes all components of society, especially in the school as the basis of citizenship education. One of the efforts to maintain and maintain and preserve the balance is the role of Citizenship Education (Civics), especially Citizenship Education is treated as an ecological education that is practically starting from school to be applied in the home environment as a practice of habituation of environmental care for virtue internalization and compassion to the wider environment (community). This argument when viewed from the point of Citizenship Education is the main estuary of Civic learning ie civic virtue.

Keywords: Citizenship Ecology, Citizenship Education, Sustainable development.

Introduction

The reality of environmental damage is currently at an alarming phase. This can be seen from the impact of environmental damage, such as the occurrence of floods in areas in remote areas of the country during the rainy season and soil cracked during the dry season so there is no natural balance in holding back rainfall as a reserve in the dry season arrived. Not to mention the behavior of citizens can not be fully aware of the importance and urgency of maintaining the balance of nature, as a result our natural environment is damaged and easy to happen landslides.

On the other hand, the flow of globalization, modernism, and technological development has crashed all sides of human life and brought great impact not only on aspects of social, economic, and political life but systemically encroaching on other aspects of life such as cultural, environmental, . It is undeniable that technological developments and the high intensity of human activities on earth have caused many destructive impacts on life networks. The most worrying thing is the occurrence of environmental imbalance that leads to various natural disasters in the form of disaster for humans and environmental damage itself.

In addition, the development of urban areas that are less attention to environmental aspects so that within the systemic framework, the situation is the cause of climate change (global climate), global warming, habitat loss, scarcity of water, pollution, floods, to the threat of hunger that is now becomes a crucial issue.

The reality of the above conditions, affirming that the consciousness of conserving and preserving the balance of the environment is very important and urgent. This followed up on the results of the world environmental conference on 5 June 1972 held by the United Nations in Stockholm which agreed on many inputs on the maintenance and control of environmental damage caused by the rise of industrialization, both in developed and developing countries. At the conference, it was also agreed on the environmental resolution that was used as the foundation

for all development. Ultimately, the conference gave birth to an environmental United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) agency headquartered in Nairobi, Kenya (Harjadasoemantri, 2000: 1).

The awareness construction of citizens on the preservation of the environment above, according to Subagyo (1999: 17), not only to create a beautiful or clean, but it has entered the human obligation to respect the rights of others. The right of the other person is to enjoy and feel the balance of nature purely, so that there is harmonization of man with nature. Cultural values is expected to give birth to local wisdom (local wisdom), which can ensure environmental sustainability.

In addition, the development of urban areas that are less attention to environmental aspects so that in the systemic framework, the situation is the cause of global warming (global warming), climate change (climate change), loss of habitat, scarcity of water, pollution, floods, Becomes a crucial issue.

Civic ecology becomes important along with the strengthening of sustainable development paradigm (sustainable development). Simply understood is development aimed at meeting the needs of present generations without compromising the ability and interests of future generations to meet their own needs. This definition refers to the World Commission on Environment and Development (WECD), a world commission for environment and development under the auspices of the United Nations. The definition contains two main concepts. Firstly, the need is very essential for the poor and needs to be prioritized. Secondly, about the limitations of environmental capability to meet the needs of present and future generations. This means long-term sustainable development (a longer-term perspective) that demands intergenerational solidarity.

The reality of the above conditions reinforces that the attention to strengthening the ecological commitment of citizenship to conserving and preserving the balance of the environment is crucial and urgent.

Literature Review

Citizenship Education

Citizenship Education is a unique and complex field of education seen from the content and content of the subject matter in terms of Civic Education as a school base education, another case when viewed from the side of social-based education. In the context of Citizenship Education in school has certain material related to material, content, curriculum and others. Nevertheless, both in the context of school-based education and social education contexts are ultimately mutually integrated in an educational objective in general, that is, they have private responsibilities and public responsibilities which both lead to good citizens and intelligent personally and socially.

Both of the above intelligence amongst them are citizens who have knowledge and mental tolerance between generations in a solid not individualistic but attention to future interests including solidarity in the context of the fulfillment of life both economically, socially and environmentally. In terms of economic, social and environmental Citizenship Education has a mission to maintain, maintain and sustainability of these three things, because these three things are important aspects and become capital in life today and in the midst of the tight competition and the swift current of globalization both in the field Economic, and social that not least impact the environment is not good. Therefore, the Civic Education Mission among others is the economic, social and environmental solidarity between generations. It is as Suryadi (1993) that among the mission of Civics is to develop state of mind, the development of the nation's character is the process of intelligent and intelligent citizen formation.

Civic education focuses on civic intelligence, civic reasonability, and citizen participation as a foundation for developing democratic values and behaviors. Democracy is developed through the expansion of insight, the development of analytical skills and social sensitivity for citizens to help them solve environmental problems. Analytical skills are also needed in connection with the political system, state, and legislation in order to solve the problems they are doing is realistic. Furthermore, said that Civic education membelajarkan students have social sensitivity and understand the problems that occur environment intelligently. From that process students can also

be expected to have high rational, emotional, social and spiritual abilities in solving social problems in society.

The Ecology of Citizenship

Strengthening environmental concerns is morally related to citizens' status to seek for the sustainability of ecosystems in nature (Dobson, 2007). The moral strengthening is by awareness of a central role that citizens have about environmental awareness. The role of the citizen is then translated into habits and behaviors. McCarney (2012) explains that the awareness is a positive participation and ability to access information about environmental care activities to seek the return of ecological carrying capacity for life. Dobson offers the completion of increasingly damaged ecological conditions with a new perspective to look at the environmental issues of citizen positions.

A new perspective by Dobson is called ecological citizenship, which is the view of every citizen along with his status as a member of a political entity called a country that has the right to enjoy a healthy life and the obligation to participate in it. That view is a virtue value based on citizenship that is more than a restricted view of a country's territory. Dobson assumes that ecological citizenship is one view that sparked an environmental and private public interest movement. This perspective also exceeds the environmental citizenship view that focuses only on environmental issues without quantifying the socio-political and economic impact of the ecological crisis (Escrhuela, 2008). This is because ecological citizenship is a derivation of ecological politics, or on the other hand considers economic citizenship as a theory of individual citizenship.

On both sides, the designer of citizenship theory sees a change in the relationships between global and local citizenship in an ecological context, using social responsibility in a citizenship area so that it can work (Saiz, 2005). Turner (2001) describes ecological citizenship as an expression of the obligation of citizens to restore the authenticity of the environment. Dobson agrees with the opinion of Mark Smith that it is time to have a view of 'a new politics of obligation' that begins to pay attention to the human obligations to animals, plants, mountains, seas and all members of the community. Dobson (2007) cautioned that the realization of ecological citizenship begins from the home environment as a practice of environmental care habituation for the virtue of virtue such as care and compassion. This view when viewed from the point of Civic Education fit into the main estuary of Civics learning. In Civic Education's review, citizen participation is shaped by elements of civic knowledge, civic virtue, civic skills, civic disposition, and civic commitment (Branson and Quigley, 1998).

Budimansyah and Suryadi (2008) also mentioned that the Civic Education paradigm ala *civitas international* and a number of centers for Civic Education also focused on the development of civic virtue and civic culture. The virtue of citizenship or civic virtue in the field of morally degraded environments is marked by the widespread destruction of forests through illegal logging, the dumping of garbage and industrial waste indiscriminately, the decline in air and water quality. This condition requires an alternative solution that includes all components of society.

Ecological citizenship is closely related to ethics, it can be understood as a philosophy or critical and fundamental thought about moral teachings and views. Ethics provides a human orientation so that people do not live by joining it to the various parties who want to determine how we should live, but so we can understand for ourselves why we should behave like this or so. Ethics help us be better able to account for our lives.

Environmental problems are an ethical issue because people often "forget" and lose their orientation in treating nature. Because of "forget" and lose that orientation, humans then treat nature irresponsibly. In such circumstances, they are no longer critical. Therefore, an ethical approach in addressing environmental issues is very necessary. The approach is primarily intended to determine the appropriate ethical attitudes, actions and ethical perspectives and management of the environment and all members of the ecosystem. So, it is only natural that the current environment of environmental ethics with the option of "friendly" to the environment.

Environmental ethics is differentiated into "conservation ethics" and "maintenance ethics". Ethical preservation is an ethic that emphasizes the pursuit of nature preservation for the

benefit of humans, while maintenance ethics is intended to support the efforts of environmental preservation for the benefit of all beings.

Environmental ethics is also called ecological ethics which is divided into two namely: "deep ecological ethics" and "shallow ecological ethics". Deep ecological ethics is an approach to the environment that sees the importance of understanding the environment as a whole of mutual life, so that all elements have the same meaning and meaning. This Ecological Ethics has the principle that all life forms have innate value and therefore have the right to demand respect for self-esteem, the right to life and the right to flourish. The premise is that the moral environment must transcend the human species by incorporating a wider community. A wider community means a community that includes animals and plants and nature. For deep ecological ethics, nature has a life-sustaining function. For that the environment is worthy of respect and treated in a good way. This ethic emphasizes the maintenance of nature not only for the sake of man but also for the sake of nature itself. Because nature is recognized as the support of human life and all creation. For that man is called to preserve nature for the common good.

While shallow ecological ethics is an approach to the environment that emphasizes that the environment as a means of human interest, which is anthropocentric. This shallow ecological ethics is usually applied to the philosophy of rationalism and humanism as well as mechanistic science which is followed and followed by many environmentalists. Most of these environmentalists have the view that nature aims to meet the needs of human life. In the context of environmental ethics then the intended good, intended for all beings.

Environmental Ethics Theory

Environmental ethics theory is expected to create a new understanding of environmental problems that are not separate from certain cosmology which in fact does not foster exploitative attitude to the natural environment. The development of environmental ethics is needed to control the fundamental changes of cosmological view that fosters respect and friendship with the natural environment (Yuniarto, 2012: 61).

There are three environmental ethical theories that can be explained to build thinking in handling ecological crises: Egocentric Ethics, Homocentric Ethics, and Ecosystem Ethics.

Egocentric Ethics

Ethics that bases itself on various individual interests (self). Egocentric is based on the individual's imperative to focus on what actions are good for him. Egocentric claims that good for the individual is good for society. The orientation of egocentric ethics is not based on narcissism, but rather based on a philosophy which focuses on separate independent individuals or groups like "social atom" (Sudriyanto 1992: 4) (Yuniarto, 2012: 62).

The essence of this egocentric view, Sonny Keraf (1990: 31) explains that the actions of each person are basically aimed at pursuing self-interest and promoting oneself. Thus, egocentric ethics based itself on human action as a rationalist to treat nature according to "neutral" instinct. It is based on various "mechanism" views on assumptions related to liberal social theory (Sudriyanto, 1992: 15 in Yuniarto, 2012: 65), namely: Mechanical knowledge is based on the assumption that everything is a separate part independently. Atoms are real components of nature. So, humans are the real components of society where the whole is the sum of the parts. The logical identity law ($A = A$) underlies the mathematical depiction of nature. Similarly, society, which is nothing but a summation of many individual rational actors, thus Mechanism has the assumption that many external causes apply in various internal parts. Similar to society, laws and rules imposed by rulers will be adhered to by the people in a positive way, Subsequent Changes can occur by rearranging the parts. The building of society's demands is determined by its parts thus mechanical science is always dualistic, as, mechanical knowledge places the individual part as the main component in the development of embossed corporates.

Thus, egocentric ethics places humans as the ultimate individual in the development of the social environment.

Homocentric Ethics

Homocentric ethics is based on the interests of some people. This ethics bases itself on various models of social interests and approaches between environmental actors protecting the vast majority of human society. The homocentric ethic is the same as the ethics of utilitarianism. Thus, if an egocentric ethic bases the judgment of good and evil of that action on the purpose and consequence of that action for the individual, then this utilitarian ethic judges the goodness of an action based on the purpose and effect of that action for as many people as possible. This homocentric or utilitarian ethic is the same as ethical universalism, because it emphasizes the good effect that is useful for as many people as possible and ethical because it emphasizes good results. It is called utilitarianism because it judges the good or bad of an action based on the usefulness or usefulness of the action (Keraf 1990: 34).

As with egocentric ethics, homocentric ethics is consistent with the assumptions of mechanical knowledge. Both nature and society are described in terms of mechanical mechanics. In modern society, every part is connected organically with other parts. The effect on this section will affect other parts. Vice versa, but because of the nature of the test utilitaris, this utilitarian ethics leads to the depletion of various natural resources under the pretext for the benefit and the good of society (Sudriyanto, 1990: 16) (Yuniarto, 2012: 70).

Ecosystem Ethics

Ecocentric ethics bases itself on the cosmos. According to this ecocentric ethic, the environment as a whole is judged on itself. This ethic, according to the high ecological ethical flow of deep ecology, is the most likely alternative to solve ecological ethical dilemmas. According to ecocentrism, the most important thing is the survival of all living and non-living as components of healthy ecosystems, like humans, all cosmic objects have their own moral responsibility (Sudriyanto 1992: 243 in Yuniarto, 2012: 72).

According to this ethic, the earth expands community bonds that include "land, water, plants and animals or collectively, the earth." Earth changed the dairy "homo sapiens" from the creatures of the earth community, became part of the composition of the citizens themselves. There is respect for other members as well as the natural community itself (Sudriyanto, 1992: 2-13 in Yuniarto, 2012: 72). Ecocentric ethics is holistic, more mechanical or metaphysical. There are five basic assumptions that implicitly exist in this holistic perspective (Sudriyanto1992) namely: Everything is interconnected. The whole is a part, otherwise the change is happening on the part that will change the other part and the whole. No part of the ecosystem can be changed without changing the dynamics of its rotation. If there are many changes that occur then there will be destruction of the ecosystem and the whole more than the sum of many parts. This can not be equated with the concept of an individual who has the emotion that the whole equals the sum of many parts.

The ecological system undergoes a synergistic process, is a separate part combination and will result in greater consequence than the sum of individual effects, and then the meaning depends on the context, as opposed to the "context independence" of the "mechanism". Each part gets its meaning in the whole context so that human nature and non-human realm are one. In holistic there is no dualism. Man and nature are part of the same organic cosmological system.

The above description will lead to the opinion of Arne Naess, a Norwegian philosopher that concern for the natural environment can be divided into two kinds, namely:

- 1) "shallow ecology" environmental awareness
- 2) "deep ecology" environmental awareness.

This ecological concern is often called the holistic platter altruism, which assumes that it has ultimate moral relevance, not the types of complainants (including individuals or societies), but nature as a whole (Sudriyanto 1992: 22 in Yuniarto, 2012: 73).

Sustainable Development

The concept of sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the current generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs "(Fauzi, 2004: 15). Fulfilling those needs is closely related to economic development. According

to Perman et al., In Fauzi (2004: 18), there are at least three main reasons why economic development should be sustainable.

First, it concerns moral reasons. Current generations who enjoy goods and services produced from natural and environmental resources have a moral obligation to leave that resource service for future generations. The moral obligation includes not destroying the environmentally destructive natural resources, thus eliminating the opportunity for future generations to enjoy the same services.

Second, concerning ecological reasons. Biodiversity for example, has a very high ecological value so that economic activity should not be directed at things that threaten the ecological function.

Third, concerning economic reasons. The reason of the economic side is still a debate because it is not known whether economic activity has been or has not met the criteria of sustainable. The economic dimension of sustainability itself is quite complex, so that often this aspect of economic sustainability is limited only to intergenerational welfare maximization.

The concept of sustainability has at least two dimensions, namely the dimension of time because sustainability is nothing else about what will happen in the future, and the dimension of the interaction between the economic system and the natural and environmental resources system (Heal in Fauzi, 2004: 23).

Yuniarto, (2012: 77) sees aspects of sustainability from different sides. He sees that sustainability has a static and dynamic sense. Static sustainability is defined as the utilization of renewable natural resources with constant technological pace, while dynamic sustainability is defined as the utilization of non-renewable natural resources with ever-changing technological levels (Fauzi, 2004: 18).

In relation to sustainable development, there are two rules that must be considered in the management of natural resources and environment, namely (Pearce and Turner, 1990: 112): For renewable resources: Harvest rates should be less than or equal to the rate of regeneration (sustainable production, and For environmental concerns: The rate of disposal (waste) should be smaller or equal to the capacity of environmental assimilation.

The operational aspect of this concept of sustainability can be understood further by the existence of five alternative definitions as described in Perman et al. (1996) in Fauzi (2004: 25), as follows: A condition is said to be sustainable if the public utility does not decrease over time and consumption does not decrease over time (non-declining consumption), Sustainability is a condition in which natural resources are managed in such a way as to maintain future production opportunities and

Sustainability is a condition in which natural capital stock does not decrease over time (non-declining), and sustainability is a condition in which natural resources are managed to maintain the production of natural resource services, and Sustainability is a condition where the minimum conditions of equilibrium and resilience of the ecosystem are met.

In addition to the above operational definition, Haris (2000) in Fauzi (2004: 30) saw that the concept of sustainability can be broken down into three aspects of understanding:

(1) Economic sustainability, defined as development that is able to produce goods and services continuously to maintain the sustainability of government and avoid the occurrence of sectoral imbalances that can damage agricultural and industrial production.

(2) Environmental sustainability: An environmentally sustainable system must be capable of maintaining stable resources, avoiding natural resource exploitation and environmental absorption functions. This concept also concerns the maintenance of biodiversity, air space stability, and other ecosystem functions that do not belong to the category of economic resources.

(3) Social sustainability: Social sustainability is defined as a system capable of achieving equality, providing social services including health, education, gender, and political accountability.

According to Munasinghe (1993: 47), sustainable development has three main objectives: economic objectives, ecological objectives and social objectives. The economic goals are related to efficiency and growth issues; Ecological objectives related to the issue of natural resource conservation; And social goals related to poverty and equity.

In the review of Sugandhy and Hakim (2007: 21) this sustainable development needs to be emphasized on the coordination and integration of natural resources, human resources and artificial resources in every national development. Thus, the goal of sustainable development basically lies in the harmonization between economic goals, ecological goals and social objectives.

The concept of sustainable development is closely linked to ethical issues, given that the concept of sustainable development is oriented towards the future and also focuses on the problem of poverty. This concept is very concerned about the welfare of future generations, but at the same time it does not diminish attention to efforts to improve the lives of the poor in the present generation (Barbier 1993: 67).

In terms of environmental ethics, sustainable development more follows the view of ecocentrism rather than the anthropocentrism view. Keraf (2002: 14) outlines the principles of environmental ethics, which, when studied further, also plays an important role in sustainable development efforts. The principles of environmental ethics referred to are:

(1) Respect for nature (respect for nature); (2) The principle of responsibility (moral responsibility for nature); (3) Cosmic solidarity; (4) Principles of love and caring for nature; (5) The principle of no harm; (6) The principle of life is simple and in harmony with nature; (7) The principle of justice; (8) The principle of democracy; and (9) Principles of moral integrity.

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